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Direct High-Frequency Modulation of a Quantum Cascade Laser for High-Sensitivity Molecular Dispersion Spectroscopy at Ambient Pressure

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Abstract—Heterodyne Phase Sensitive Dispersion Spectroscopy has emerged as a promising new approach to gas-phase chemical sensing. The most common implementation of this method uses direct modulation of the injection current of a quantum cascade laser. The modulation produces a three-tone optical signal which, when passed through the gas sample, allows the profile of the refractive index, from which the gas concentration can be derived, to be measured. However, the frequency of this modulation signal must be in the range of the linewidth of the target molecular resonance, which for many compounds of interest is in the few GHz at ambient pressure. This challenging requirement prevents the technique from operating in free space with good sensitivity. Nevertheless, in this article, we present a novel quantum cascade laser package that, together with a simple and reliable Heterodyne Phase Sensitive Dispersion Spectroscopy instrument design, demonstrates a very convincing solution to overcome the performance limitations of current systems at ambient pressure, hence enabling high performance gas analysis in free space. Various experiments targeting methane at 1311.5 cm^{-1} show excellent linearity over a concentration range of four orders of magnitude and a limit of detection which is well into the sub-ppm-m.

Index Terms—High-frequency modulation, heterodyne phase sensitive dispersion spectroscopy (HPSDS), quantum cascade laser (QCL), ambient pressure gas sensing.

I. INTRODUCTION

OPTICAL absorption spectroscopy, which is based on the measurement of the absorption profile of the molecular resonances of interest, is a well-known technique in research and analytical chemistry laboratories as well as in industry, with a wide variety of long-established applications ranging from chemical process monitoring to security and safety [1-4]. This method has benefited greatly from the technological sophistication of

modern semiconductor lasers, which offer an unrivalled combination of spectral power density and practicality of use as small, robust and high-performance devices. The simplest spectroscopic approaches perform a single measurement, or a wavelength sweep, of the optical absorption around the absorption line of the target molecule to retrieve the concentration of that gas [5,6]. However, more complex approaches, such as the use of very fast scans of the absorption line [7] or wavelength modulated emitters [8,9], allow a significant improvement in the performance of the systems. This set of methods has been complemented, albeit only in the last decade, by the emerging field of molecular dispersion spectroscopy [10,11]. This new but well-established technique uses a measurement of the profile of the refractive index of the sample in the vicinity of the molecular transitions of interest, rather than the absorption profile, to determine the concentration of gas. The specific profile of the refractive index induces changes in the phase velocity (optical dispersion) of the optical signal in a degree that is directly proportional to the gas concentration. Therefore, the obtaining of this refractive index profile makes it possible to determine, in addition to other parameters, the gas concentration. Nowadays, various methods can be used to get access to the dispersion profile of a gaseous sample. Apart from more dated measurement approaches [12], modern molecular dispersion spectroscopy methods can be divided into those that characterize the refractive index profile from either a frequency or a phase analysis of the beat note generated after detecting the optical signal employed to interrogate the sample of interest.

The first branch, called Chirped Laser Dispersion Spectroscopy (CLaDS) [10,13-16], was the first to be developed, while the second branch, which focuses on phase measurement and among which Heterodyne Phase Sensitive Dispersion Spectroscopy (HPSDS) [11,17-20] stands out, is a slightly more recent proposal that also features a simplified system architecture (even allowing the design of hybrid systems with a joint implementation of dispersion and absorption spectroscopy [21]). These two spectroscopic techniques (CLaDS and HPSDS) have demonstrated very important advantages over systems using optical absorption measurement. First of all, these developments offer opportunities to solve the well-known baseline and normalization problems of traditional techniques [8, 9]. More importantly, molecular dispersion spectroscopy methods provide an output that is, in a properly designed system [10,11], linearly dependent on the concentration of the target gas,

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resulting in an extended dynamic range and constant sensitivity over the whole range. An additional advantage, which is a direct consequence of the measurement of dispersion (rather than intensity), is the immunity of the gas concentration measurement to variations in the received optical power [17]. This system strength is of particular interest in free space measurements, where the optical beam, and the various components, may be exposed to dusty environments or vibrations that produce optical power variations of different characteristics. Nonetheless, the analysis at high performance levels of gaseous samples at ambient pressure with molecular dispersion spectroscopic techniques is still a considerable challenge for various reasons. Addressing these problems, particularized for HPSDS, is precisely the focus of this paper.

The basics of HPSDS operation have been covered in detail in several publications [11,17-20], but for the sake of completeness, the key concepts are briefly outlined here. Focusing on the mid-infrared range, where the impact of these techniques is most prominent, the most basic HPSDS implementation consists of a laser that is directly (injection current) modulated at high frequency in order to generate a three-tone optical signal. When this composite signal is passed through the sample, the different refractive indices experienced by each of the tones result in different phase velocities, creating optical phase shifts between the three optical tones. These phase shifts, which are linearly dependent on gas concentration, can be conveniently measured by analyzing the phase of the RF signal generated when the optical beam is impinged on a photodiode. Nevertheless, in order to optimize the detection capabilities of the target gas, it is of the utmost importance to select the appropriate modulation frequency, as previously demonstrated in the initial publication introducing the HPSDS method [11]. It can be seen, therefore, that although HPSDS signals can be obtained at almost any modulation frequency, there is an optimum point at which the amplitude of the dispersion signal is maximized, thereby leading to an optimal performance of the system. To achieve this, the laser modulation frequency must be set to a value close to the linewidth of the molecular transition of interest (approximately 58% of it, although this may vary slightly with different sources) [11]. Unfortunately, at ambient pressure, the linewidth of molecular transitions for a large number of molecules of interest is several GHz, which means that for optimal performance, modulation frequencies in the same range must be used. Therefore, it is quite common to find publications using gaseous samples at low pressures with dispersion-based methods [10, 13, 17]. This need for high modulation frequencies makes the regular HPSDS system impractical for use in ambient conditions. The technological maturity and availability of RF generators and components operating in the GHz range is not currently in question, but there are two main instrumental factors that limit their use in this type of spectroscopic system. On the one hand, fast (> 1 GHz) and convenient to use mid-infrared photodetectors have only recently become commercially available. On the other hand, the design of the robust and widely used High Heat Load (HHL) laser package is very inadequate for fast modulation of the laser current.

In this article, we present a novel Quantum Cascade Laser

(QCL) package, developed by Alpes Lasers, and the system in which it is integrated, which proves to be the adequate route to overcome the performance limitations of HPSDS systems at ambient pressure. With operating frequencies well above 1 GHz, the new design easily enables high performance gas detection in free space. In addition to a detailed characterization of the system, the article includes a performance comparison with a regular HHL packaged laser, which clearly illustrates the tremendous capabilities of this new development for molecular dispersion spectroscopy.

II. QCL PACKAGING

At the core of the new device lies a DFB-QCL from Alpes Lasers. The emitter, with a ridge waveguide width of 8.5 μm (measured at the center of the active region) and a cavity length of 2.25 mm, has a grating period of 1.2 μm , processed as buried heterostructure [22]. A high reflectivity gold coating was deposited on the back facet. The active region of the QCL is an unstrained design centred at 1280 cm^{-1} . Various photographs of the device can be seen in Fig. 1(a). In general, the device operates in single-mode over a temperature range of -10 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and has a tuning range that extends from 1306 to 1314 cm^{-1} . The DFB-QCL can provide power levels above 100 mW and has a maximum operation current of 420 mA for all temperatures within the operating range.

The QCL was placed into a Laboratory Laser Housing (LLH), a versatile packaging designed for research applications with a size of 100 x 50 x 50 mm. The housing, which in this case needs to be water cooled, has the standard embedded thermoelectric cooler for the accurate control of the temperature of the laser. However, in order to enable high frequency current modulation, the current source is connected to the device using a SMA connector fixed on the LLH lid. To minimize losses, a coaxial cable was employed to link the laser to this SMA connector. For light collimation, additional threaded holes were machined in the front of the housing to allow the use of a cage system, translating lens mount; a lens with an effective focal length of 1.873 mm was employed. Several photographs of the assembly are shown in Fig. 1(b).

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Fig. 1. Photographs of the laser and the LLH package. a) photographs of the backside, at the top left, front side, at the top right, and the top of the unit, at the bottom of the figure. b) LLH packaging, including, at the top left, the laser wiring and, at the top right, SMA connector fixed on the LLH lid together with a pneumatic connector for pumping nitrogen into the device to prevent condensation.

III. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The HPSDS architecture implemented for the experimental validation presented in this paper is shown in Fig. 2. As introduced earlier, the method requires the laser to be precisely tuned to sweep the target spectral line and, besides this, injection current modulated to generate the three-tone optical signal. To resolve the first aspect (line sweeping), a signal generator is connected to the analog modulation input of the current driver employed (QCL500 OEM, Wavelength Electronics) to externally tune the current injected into the QCL with a sawtooth waveform of 1 Hz (90% duty cycle). The RF signal used to modulate the laser at high frequency is provided by a RF signal generator (APSIN20G, AnaPico). To overcome frequency limitations of the current driver (2 MHz bandwidth), the RF signal is added to the QCL operating current via a bias tee (ZFBT-352-FT+, Mini-circuits) connected directly to the SMA port fixed on the QCL-LLH lid. It is important to note that this device has been selected mainly for its low inductance value, which maximizes the safety of the laser by minimizing the possibility of voltage spikes in the event of abrupt current changes. For the control of the temperature operating point of the QCL, a temperature controller (PTC5K-CH, Wavelength Electronics) is used together with the thermoelectric cooler embedded in the LLH package and a recirculating chiller (T155P, ThermoTek) for a water-cooled operation. In addition, because the laser is not sealed, a flow of nitrogen was maintained in the packaging, also supplied through the lid, to prevent condensation in the QCL. The output beam from the laser is collimated using an externally adapted translating lens arrangement and, in this calibration and test experiments, passed through a 100 mm gas cell

filled with methane (in a nitrogen matrix) at precisely controlled concentrations. The detection of the three-tone optical signal that emerges after passing through the gas cell is performed by a wideband amplified photodetector (UHSM-10.6, VIGO Photonics) with a measured cut-off frequency of 1.3 GHz. This detector delivers a beat tone, obviously with a frequency equal to the modulation frequency of the QCL, with a phase that depends on the concentration of the target gas. To get access to this information, the beat note is frequency down shifted to an intermediate frequency of 200 kHz using a frequency mixer (ZEM-4300+, Mini-circuits) and a local oscillator (second output channel of the RF generator) for analysis via a regular lock-in amplifier (MFLI – 5 MHz, Zurich Instruments). It is important to note that the RF signal generator and the lock-in amplifier were synchronized to ensure optimal functioning.

Fig. 2. Architecture of the Heterodyne Phase Sensitive Dispersion Spectroscopy system. RC, Recirculating Chiller; TC, Temperature Controller; CD, Current Driver; RFSG, Radio Frequency Signal Generator; QCL, Quantum Cascade Laser; BT, Bias tee; GC, Gas Cell; PD, Photodetector; M, Frequency Mixer. RFSG1 is connected to CD for the DC current bias and wavelength sweeping of the QCL, then the high frequency modulation signal is coupled to the laser through the BT.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental validation tests involve analyzing a molecular transition of methane in the vicinity of 1311.5 cm^{-1} ($7.62 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$). To control the gas concentration, a gas mixer using different flow controllers (F-201CV-1K0, F-201CV-100, Bronkhorst) was employed to create different gas samples in the gas cell. The desired concentration was achieved by adjusting the flow ratio of methane to nitrogen via control software. To begin the analysis of the system performance, it should be made clear that the limiting component in terms of maximum modulation frequency is the photodetector used. It can be added that the frequency response of this detector was characterized using a complex optical signal created using electro-optic modulators operating in the near-infrared range, which was then shifted to the mid-infrared range by Difference Frequency Generation (the system used is similar to the one presented in reference [23]). With this arrangement it is straightforward to generate monochromatic optical signals with a relative distance that can be freely controlled between zero and up to several GHz by simply adjusting the RF signal to be injected into two electro-optic modulators operating in parallel. By applying this optical signal to the detector, sweeping the RF

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frequency offset and monitoring the amplitude of the output beat note with a spectrum analyzer, the bandwidth of the detector can be promptly characterized. The frequency response obtained, normalized to the passband amplitude, is shown in Fig. 3.

Following the characterization of the photodetector response, this measurement was used to compare the modulation frequency performance of the experimental LLH packaging used in our system and a traditional HHL packaging. It should be noted that a DFB-QCL with HHL packaging from the same laser manufacturer was used for this test. This device has an implementation and performance almost identical to the one mounted in the new LLH packaging (the operating range of this second QCL goes from 1308 cm^{-1} to 1315 cm^{-1}). The modulation signal was combined with the injection current using exactly the same bias tee model, obviously keeping all other system components the same. To try to minimize the influence of the components used, the bias tee was also connected to an SMA connector which was soldered to pin connectors allowing very good contact with the pins of the HHL packaging.

The results of the frequency response characterization of the two laser modulation schemes, in the new LLH packaging and in the traditional HHL packaging, have been superimposed in Fig. 3. In the case of HHL packaging, there is a very clear drop in signal amplitude at high frequencies, with a 3 dB cut-off frequency around 750 MHz, but with a very pronounced drop for frequencies above 1 GHz. This means that this range of modulation frequencies cannot be used with this device. In contrast, the new LLH package design with SMA connector has a frequency response that overlaps almost perfectly with that of the detector used. Consequently, this can be interpreted as meaning that the cut-off frequency of the modified LLH package and laser assembly is significantly higher than the cut-off frequency of the detector used. Therefore, the limitation of the maximum modulation frequency of the implemented system is actually limited by the photodetector.

Fig. 3. Frequency response of the photodetector together with the responses at different modulation frequencies of the LLH and HHL lasers.

Turning now to the analysis of the functioning of the HPSDS system, the first step in studying the performance of the implemented HPSDS system was to determine an adequate operation point (QCL temperature and DC current) based on the laser characteristics. As a concise representation, Fig. 4 shows the output phase signal measured by the HPSDS system at

ambient pressure (947 hPa) for a concentration of 1% of methane in a 100 mm gas cell with the QCL operating at two different temperatures ($10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $12 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and a modulation frequency of 1.5 GHz. All the results presented correspond to an integration time on the lock-in amplifier of 10 ms and 8-order low pass filter. The high gas concentration employed ensures maximum consistency and representativeness in the results of this first phase of the system characterization. The results presented are in clear agreement with expectations, with a lateral shift of the molecular transition as the temperature sweeps and a signal that is noticeably dependent on the injected current. As has been previously demonstrated in the literature (although at lower operating frequencies) [17,24], and as a consequence of the distinctive frequency modulation characteristics of QCLs [25], the greater the bias current injected into the laser, the greater the modulation in the laser emission wavelength in relation to its intensity modulation. This moves the laser further away from its ideal configuration, where only intensity modulation should be present, slightly increasing the phase signal for a given concentration, but marginally decreasing the linearity of the gas concentration measurement. This feature enables the adjustment of the performance of the gas detection system towards higher sensitivity or higher linearity, within a range that is dependent on the laser used. This provides additional flexibility in the performance of the instrument for application to different scenarios.

Fig. 4. Phase shift retrieved by the HPSDS system after passing through the 100 mm gas cell filled with methane at a concentration of 1000 ppm-m and ambient pressure. Two signals, obtained at different operation temperature configurations of the QCL, are shown.

The following experiments now focus on characterizing the performance of the implemented HPSDS system based on the new LLH packaging. For the present validation and characterization of the system performance, a temperature of $12 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ has been selected in order to maximize linearity. Additionally, as illustrated in the HITRAN simulation shown in Fig. 5, the FWHM of the selected absorption line is around 3.3 GHz (0.11 cm^{-1}), which would ideally imply that the optimal modulation frequency is approximately 2 GHz [11,17]. However, due to the limited frequency response of the photodetector, the intensity of the beat note drops significantly at this frequency, preventing adequate signal-to-noise ratios. For this reason, it has been decided to limit the modulation frequency to 1.5 GHz, which delivers very good amplitude

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signals and only represents a reduction of about 2.5 % of the maximum achievable sensitivity [11].

Fig. 5. CH₄ absorption line for 3000 ppm·m at 1311.5 cm⁻¹ with Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM) highlighted.

Relevant factors to evaluate the performance of the HPSDS system, such as linearity and sensitivity are discussed by analyzing the calibration curve of the system, additionally the limit of detection (LOD) is also evaluated. To obtain this calibration curve, several concentrations of methane gas at ambient pressure were pumped into the gas cell and measured with the system. The output HPSDS phase signal corresponding to the different measured gas concentrations are shown in Fig. 6(a). The various HPSDS signals show the very clear dependence of their amplitude on the methane concentration, however, to make this more evident, the absolute value of the valley amplitude of the signal has been isolated and plotted as a function of concentration on Fig. 6(b).

Fig. 6. a) HPSDS phase signal output for several concentrations. b) Calibration curve of the instrument (absolute valley amplitude of the HPSDS signal vs gas concentration).

The calibration curve, obtained using simple linear regression based on ordinary least squares, resulted in an R-squared (R^2) value of 0.99 with a sensitivity of 8.305×10^{-3} %/ppm·m testifying to the very high linearity of the system. For this evaluation, the measurement at 5000 ppm·m was left aside, since for this concentration, as is evident in the graph, the linearity range of the system is already exceeded. If we stick to the linear range, up to 3000 ppm·m, the linearity error has been evaluated by extracting exclusively the absolute valley value of the signal for individual measurements and without any processing of the measurements. A value of 0.81 % normalized to full scale was obtained. This shows the very high consistency of the proposed system.

From the above set of measurements, the LOD value was estimated by calculating the noise level equivalent methane concentration (1σ). For the evaluation of this noise level, the baseline noise away from the molecular resonance has been characterized, as shown in the inset of Fig. 6a. The value obtained, compensated for the sensitivity of the system and the integration time used, gives a LOD of 0.33 ppm·m/Hz^{1/2}. It should be noted that the LOD obtained in this case is limited by etalons formed within the optical windows of the cell used for calibration. This is justified in Fig. 7, which shows the HPSDS phase signal output recovered for a reduced concentration of 7.5 ppm·m. The FFT analysis of this signal, shown in the inset, reveals clear frequency peaks that correspond to the modulation effect introduced by the intensity modulation on the etalons in the system (it can be added that HPSDS is far superior in terms of etalon robustness to intensity-based systems [17]). The calculations performed, considering the transformation between the FFT points and the corresponding FSR, associate the main peak, the one with the highest frequency found, to an FSR of 0.29 nm. This corresponds to an optical path length of 98.9 mm, a value that fits the cell length with an error of 1%. This analysis suggests that the current LOD is limited by the gas cell employed and that the LOD in free space may be significantly higher than the one provided above. In any case, of all the specifications of the system, we believe that it is very important to highlight the excellent linearity of the instrument, with a linear range of four orders of magnitude going from the LOD (assuming integration times of 1 s) to around 3000 ppm·m.

Fig. 7. HPSDS phase signal output retrieved for a concentration of 7.5 ppm·m, with an inset showing its Fast Fourier Transform (FFT).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In the present work, an HPSDS system based on a novel LLH

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QCL package developed by Alpes Lasers for the detection of gases at ambient pressure has been experimentally validated. For the implementation of the HPSDS system, the optical signal generation is performed by direct modulation of the laser injection current, resulting in simple and robust system designs. In relation to the experimental tests, firstly, the frequency responses of the detector, a limiting factor at present, and the high-frequency modulation capabilities of the new LLH packaging and the traditional HHL packaging were experimentally characterized. The results show the excellent performance of the new design in terms of high-frequency modulation capability. While the regular HHL packaging exhibits strong attenuation at high frequencies, the new LLH design allows the limits imposed by the photodetector used in the system to be comfortably exceeded. This prevents traditional packaging from approaching the optimal modulation frequencies that allow maximization of gas detection capabilities, which, as demonstrated in this paper, the new LLH package does.

Regarding the performance characteristics of the implemented HPSDS instrument, these were analyzed using methane as target gas. A 100 mm optical length cell, in which different methane concentrations were created, was used as the basis for the performance analysis of the instrument. The results analysis yielded a very high level of linearity ($R^2 = 0.99$) over a concentration range up to 3000 ppm·m with a non-linearity error of 0.81 % obtained from direct extraction of the absolute valley value of the signal, without any intermediate processing or signal fitting. This gives an indication of the good response of the instrument. It can be added that the non-linearity error is of the same magnitude as the accuracy of the flow controllers, so that this error should not be associated exclusively with the implemented HPSDS system. Although this article focuses on validating the capabilities of new QCL packaging for the HPSDS method rather than maximizing the performance of the system, the LOD found, limited by interference fringes, is of 0.33 ppm·m/Hz^{1/2}, which is a more than remarkable value for the operating range of the laser used. It could be added that a change in the emission wavelength to 3000 cm⁻¹ could improve the performance of the system by almost an order of magnitude. However, we have chosen to stick to the operating range presented here because of the availability of components. In summary, these results demonstrate the ideality of the developed packaging for use in free-space molecular dispersion spectroscopy applications.

It should be noted that the implementation of the packaging still has limitations for use outside the laboratory, such as the need for water cooling, the fact that it is not sealed, or the lack of collimating optics integrated in the packaging. However, work is currently underway to integrate lasers in a package similar to HHL, but with SMA connection and coaxial access to the device. This development, which is expected to be completed in the short term, would directly address all the limitations of the device used. In addition, the growing interest in the mid-infrared band for communications will undoubtedly have a very positive impact on the technological development

of laser sources and detectors with high-frequency operating capabilities. To the author's opinion, it is clear that all these factors will make it possible in the short to medium term to overcome the current barriers and to have molecular dispersion spectroscopy systems operating in open space and at high pressures with optimum performance.

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